

**Learning to Learn and Productivity Growth:
Evidence from a New Car-Assembly Plant**

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Abstract

This paper models learning by experience beyond the experience curve, including the possibility of “learning to learn”: the speed of learning increases over time by building on what has already been learned. We compare the extended deterministic learning model with Jovanovic and Nyarkos’ [26] stochastic learning. Finally, the theoretical models are tested with data on total factor productivity of a car-assembly plant in its first months of operation. We find that the deterministic “mixed learning model”, where the speed of learning is equal to a constant plus a learning to learn effect, is the one that best fits the empirical data. The mixed learning model results in a time pattern of total factor productivity growth, first increasing and later decreasing, different from the always decreasing rate of growth of the learning curve, opening new perspectives on the study of learning by experience.

Key words: Organizational learning, learning by experience, total factor productivity, production function, car-assembly plant.

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1.-Introduction

Productivity, or the rate at which input quantities are turned into outputs, receives a lot of attention at the macro (as determinant of differences in the per capita income of countries [43]), at the firm (as explanatory of differences in competitiveness and profitability of firms [6]) and at the operational level (explaining differences in efficiency and costs across production units [35]). Most of the recent productivity research has concentrated in explaining the observed differences in productivity levels across firms within and between industries and countries (Syverson [41], for a review). Much less is known, however, on what determines the time path of productivity for an individual production unit, even though macro productivity growth comes from the aggregation of efficiency gains at the production unit level.

The existing explanations of productivity gains at the micro level are mainly two. One of them considers productivity growth the consequence of a general time trend of technological progress that continuously expands output at rates faster than the growth in inputs¹. The other explanation is rooted in the learning curve where the rate of productivity growth is positive but decreases over time (Zangwill and Kantor [48], for a formal generalization of the learning curve). The first explanation implicitly assumes “Schumpeterian” innovation, constantly reinventing the production technology as well as the products and services sold in the market. The second one takes the production technology and products’ attributes as constant and productivity gains are the result of continuous and gradual improvements in the ways things are done in the production process.

This paper advances in the explanation of productivity growth proposing a general model of learning by experience. The model includes unlimited technical progress and the learning curve as particular cases but it covers two additional forms of “deterministic” learning. The model is formulated at the level of an operating unit, i.e. production plant, and it is applied to study the learning process behind the observed

¹ Technical progress is the result of successful practical applications of scientific, technical and organizational discoveries sustained by research, development and innovation. Technical progress as explanation of productivity growth is connected with the pioneer work of Solow [41] who first described productivity growth as a “residual” reflecting the causes behind this growth that are unknown for the researcher. Research on productivity and on productivity growth can then be viewed as the search for explanations of why there are differences in the levels of output produced with similar combinations of inputs like labour and capital [42].

productivity growth in a car-assembly plant in the first years of operations. The measure of productivity used in the analysis is invariant to the intensity of capital and labour inputs used in production, i.e. it captures the total factor productivity (TFP) of the plant. We do not observe the actual actions taken by managers and workers to improve the efficiency of the production process but rather we postulate a relationship between the underlying process of discovering and application of better ways of doing things, and the observed track of improvement in terms of measured TFP. In addition, the paper includes a comparison between the proposed class of deterministic models with the “stochastic” learning model of Jovanovic and Nyarko [26].

We find that the learning model that best fits with the empirical data is what we call *mixed learning*, i.e., workers and managers of the plant combine a fixed speed of learning with a “learning to learn” capability as more knowledge is acquired. The mixed learning model implies that the results of learning in this plant translate into a first period of accelerated productivity growth, followed by another period of decelerated growth, until the maximum level of operating efficiency is attained. This is precisely what we observe in the data. Other learning models, such as the exponential version of the learning curve and Jovanovic and Nyarko’s [26] stochastic learning model, do not capture the S shape in the evolution of TFP over time. Although the evidence is obtained from a single plant, the results of the paper suggest that the existing explanations of TFP growth, such as generalized technical progress and the learning curve are incomplete and other forms of deterministic learning such as learning to learn or mixed learning should also be considered.

As for the relation of the paper with the existing literature, the theory section of the paper is in line with Zangwill and Kantor [48], who model the process of continuous improvement compatible with the learning curve [4, 47] as evidence of such improvement. Our paper is different in that we model the process of learning without limiting the results of the process to those compatible with the evidence of the learning curve. In fact, as said before the pattern of performance improvement of the learning curve is one of four possible results in the class of “deterministic” learning models.

The learning curve, and in general learning by doing, has been applied to units of varying complexity, from single machines (especially scheduling problems, [9, 24]) to

plants [1, 39] and firms [46, 31, 6]. The performance measures considered in prior research include cost [47, 48, 39], productivity [1, 6], quality [15] as well as complex measures such as overall equipment effectiveness [46].

This paper is unique in that the learning unit is a start-up assembly plant, which enables us to study learning at the moment of time when it can be expected to be particularly important. The plant produces a homogeneous output and we have monthly data on number of cars assembled. The time interval between measurements of performance is then short and the effects of learning on performance are observed shortly after management decisions, spurred by what has been learned, are implemented. The monthly frequency of observations assures enough observations to estimate the learning model for a total time period when the car model assembled in the plant, remained unchanged as well as the main parameters of the production function different from the TFP parameter. The parameters of the production function are estimated jointly with those that capture the features of the learning process using the Error Correction Method [17], which is another innovation of the paper. TFP has been used before as an indicator of the results of the learning process at the firm and industry level, but not often, if at all, at the plant level.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a description of the theories of learning and their respective analytical formulations for empirical estimation purposes. Section 3 contains the application of the theory to the case study of the assembly plant. Finally, in section 4, we present the discussion of our results and the main conclusions of our paper.

2.-Learning theories and proposed models

2.1.- A brief review of the literature

There are three main learning mechanisms identified in the extensive literature on this topic [2]. In one of them individuals and groups learn from their own experience, refining the procedures that have been previously set as the most effective way to perform the assigned tasks. This mechanism is known as *learning-by-experience* [4, 47, 3]. In another mechanism individuals combine repetition with trial and error

experimentation, intending to extract information about individual or group capabilities and about their absorptive capacity. A mechanism defined as *matching* [34, 29, 26]. Finally, individuals learn from the observation of the behaviour and performance of others, or *social learning* [20, 33]. The learning by experience mechanism is modelled as a *deterministic* process, while the matching mechanism has *stochastic* properties. In deterministic learning there is an optimal way to perform the tasks that is known by all the collaborating agents, although internal forces condition the speed at which individuals and groups converge towards the optimal solution. When learning takes place in a stochastic environment individuals do not exactly know the best way of performing an activity, since the observed outcomes from such a best way must be progressively inferred from a noisy signal.

Organizational learning and its translation into higher performance of firms, i.e. cost, productivity, quality, profits and the like, has been extensively studied in the operations, management and economics literature. The research strategies vary. At the highest level, researchers look at organizational learning as an endogenous resource that depends on factors such as the absorptive capacity of the organization [14, 19]; the organization's culture [38]; and the transfer mechanisms from one part of the organization to the other [13]. At one level below, research on learning looks at the irruption in the market of new ways of organizing work and of managing those involved, and investigates the speed at which innovations are adopted and diffused among firms in one or several industries². In this vein, there are papers that go one step further and investigate the link between the adoption of new forms of work organization and human resource management practices, and the observed operating and financial performance of firms³. Another line of research focuses on the measurement of the performance of firms over time, productivity growth for example, and explains the performance as a function of some modelled learning process. Most of the research around the learning curve referenced above follows this approach. This is also the methodology followed in this paper, with TFP as the performance measure to track the improvements.

2.2-Deterministic learning models

² See for example: Osterman [36], Ichniowski and Shaw [22], Cappelli et al [11].

³ See the papers of Adler and Clark [1], Jones and Kato [25], Ichniowski and Shaw [22], Ichniowski, Shaw and Pernushi [23], Cappelli and Neumark [12], Kato and Morishima [28], Lieberman and Dhawan [31], Ben-Ner and Lluís [8].

Let $Q(t) = A(t)F(K, L; t)$ be the production function that summarizes a state of knowledge in a moment of time about the production of a good or service, in our case the assembly of cars. $Q(t)$ is the output flow in period t ; K is the level of capital input services; L is the level of labour input services; t refers to the time period; and $A(t)$ is the total factor productivity parameter measuring the level of operating efficiency in period t . The learning models considered in the paper explain the time evolution of the TFP term $A(t)$ for cases where the other parameters in $F(K, L; t)$ remain constant over time (the time variable t applies only to input quantities). This is a standard assumption in studies that explain TFT as a result of learning by experience, where additionally it is assumed that the parameters in $F(K, L; t)$ are the same for all plants and firms (see Balasubramanian and Lieberman [6] for example). We believe that the assumption is appropriate for our empirical analysis because data come from only one production unit, and during several months when the plant operated produced the same car model with an invariant technology, plant layout and organization structure.

The actual functional form or time dynamics for $A(t)$ varies across the different studies. For example, the hypothesis of permanent and constant growth implies $A(t) = A(0)e^{gt}$, where g is the constant growth rate. A popular functional form used to represent the deterministic learning curve in the social sciences [18, 37] is $dA(t)/dt = \beta[A^* - A(t)]$ for $A(0)$ known and where β and A^* are constant. This function captures the scope of learning $A^*/A(0)$ (ratio between maximum and minimum TFP) and the speed of learning β .

In this paper we explore more flexible forms of representing the learning process and propose the following equation on the time motion of the observed performance of such process, to be validated by the empirical evidence:

$$\frac{dA(t)}{dt} = \left(\beta + \alpha \frac{A(t)}{A^*}\right)(A^* - A(t)) \quad (1)$$

The left-hand side of the equation is the absolute change in TFP in period t . The right-hand side has two terms. One of the terms, $(A^* - A(t))$, is the difference between the

maximum level of operating efficiency of the process or target of the learning process, A^* , and the current level of operating efficiency that results from past learning, $A(t)$. Thus, the difference $(A^* - A(t))$ is the stock of knowledge that is still pending incorporation into the production process, in period t . When A^* is known the learning process belongs to the class of deterministic learning models. Deterministic learning is realistic in our empirical analysis because the plant belongs to a leading world-wide car manufacturer with a lot of experience and therefore with knowledge on efficiency standards for assembly plants with a given technology.

The other term on the right-hand side of (1), $(\beta + \alpha \frac{A(t)}{A^*})$, is the *speed of learning*, defined as the proportion of the pending stock knowledge that is learned in period t . The parameters β and α , are non-negative and, depending on their values, the learning process takes one form or another as follows.

Constant learning.- One version of model (1) is what we call the constant learning process, which corresponds to the parameters' values: $\beta > 0$ and $\alpha = 0$. Now, the speed of learning will be constant and equal to β . In this situation, the organizational learning capability, the proportion of the knowledge still pending to be acquired in period t , is exogenously given and remains constant throughout the whole learning process. The general model includes then previous models of learning by experience, referenced before, as a particular case.

Learning to learn.- Another version of model (1), unexplored in the literature, corresponds to the parameters' values: $\beta = 0$ and $\alpha > 0$. The speed of learning is now equal to $\alpha \frac{A(t)}{A^*}$ and it varies over time as a function of the ratio between accumulated knowledge up to t , $A(t)$, and total potential knowledge A^* . The speed of learning at a given moment of time is an increasing function of the learning accumulated up to t , relative to the total potential cumulative learning. Since the speed at which the organization learns today is a function of the past cumulative learning, we interpret this result as evidence that the learning capability of the organization increases over time with the accumulated relative knowledge. This is the reason we define this learning model as *learning to learn*. Notice that what determines the speed of learning is not the

absolute value of the knowledge acquired by past learning, but this value relative to the maximum possible knowledge that can be acquired.

Learning to learn with unlimited knowledge model.- A special case of interest in the learning to learn model is when A^* tends to infinity. Under this additional assumption, together with $\beta=0$, equation (1) is written as $\frac{dA(t)}{dt} = \alpha A(t)$. The learning to learn process, together with the assumption that the stock of knowledge that results from the learning process is unlimited, implies that TFP will increase over time at a constant rate equal to α .

Mixed learning model.- The general formulation of model (1), where the two parameters β and α are positive, can then be described a *mixed learning* model. It combines exogenously given, constant, organizational learning capability, together with acquired learning capabilities from already accumulated knowledge. The relative importance of each component of the process in a particular production environment is an empirical question.

Technically, equation (1), and the variations under different values of the learning parameters, are differential equations that can be solved for the function that gives the time evolution of the level of TFP, $A(t)$. Table 1 shows a summary of the functional forms of $A(t)$ obtained by solving the respective differential equations, as well as the graphical representation of the respective function $A(t)$.

The process of constant learning implies a time profile of the level of TFP increasing, but at a decreasing rate ($A(t)$ is an increasing and concave function of time t)⁴. The case

⁴ The constant learning model contains the learning curve model as a special case. Zangwill and Kantor [48] derive three mathematical formulations of the learning curve from modelling a continuous improvement process where managers take an action, observe the results and learn how to improve the process in a new round. Each formulation expresses the observable outcome from continuous learning as, respectively, a potential, exponential and “finite” function of cumulative production. The potential functional form is the most extended one in the literature (where cost of n -esima unit produced is a log linear function of n -esima unit of cumulative output), but the exponential function is also used in some other papers, for example Wang and Lee [46]. Our model of constant speed of learning expresses TFP over time as an exponential function of time; if production per unit of time remains relatively constant over time, then the cumulative output is the production per period times the number of time periods, so in this case, the exponential function of time will coincide, except for a constant, with the exponential learning curve.

of learning to learn implies a time profile of TFP always increasing too, but now the rate of increase is first increasing and later decreasing ($A(t)$ is a logistic function of time with the well known S shape). In the particular case of learning to learn with unlimited bound in knowledge, the level of TFP is an increasing and convex function of time (the slope is increasing with time). This implies also that the log of $A(t)$ will be a linear function of time. Finally, the mixed learning model gives a profile of the level of TFP over time that is first convex and, after some inflexion point, becomes concave (S shaped functional form). The profile is then similar to that resulting from learning to learn, but the functional form resulting from the mixed learning model is more flexible because it has two parameters, β and α .

2.3.-Stochastic model

In the stochastic learning models, individuals involved in production (managers, technicians, workers...) do not know the standards of full efficiency of the production process in which they participate, i.e. A^* is unknown, and perform experiments trying to discover them. The model of Jovanovic and Nyarko [26] is one of the most general formulations of learning by experimentation in an environment of uncertainty and noise. The model assumes that managers and workers have an a priori estimate of the most efficient way to perform a task and update this estimate from the information contained in the result observed after each trial. The process of learning, updating knowledge, is then tied to the number of trials, repeated experience. The number of trials can be converted into time-related experience by modifying the model with a parameter that converts trials to number of time periods. This parameter will be process-specific since the number of times a task is repeated per unit of time will vary across products and technologies.

The model is formalized as follows. Consider a process or activity with N tasks where there is a maximum efficiency level for each task a_j^* , for $j=1, \dots, N$. The current level of efficiency for task j is given by $a(t)_j$ and the total level of efficiency for the process with N tasks is equal to:

$$A(t) = A\Pi(1 - (a_j^* - a(t)_j)^2), j = 1, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

When $N=1$ the activity or process is assumed to be *simple* and for higher values of N the process is described as *complex* (complexity increases with N).

The level of maximum efficiency for activity j is not known for certain; what is known is that the value is drawn from a joint probability distribution with unknown mean θ_j and known variance σ_{θ}^2 . In each time period, there is a realization of the process in terms of observed level of efficiency, $a(t)_j$ that results from the application to production of the existing knowledge. This observed values will be the realizations of the independent and identically distributed random variables $a(t)_j = \theta_j + \omega_{jt}$ where ω_{jt} are independent normally distributed random variables with mean zero and variance σ_{ω}^2 . The variable ω_{jt} is a noise that distorts the information of the signal about the true value of the mean of the distribution, θ_j .

The application of a Bayesian revision mechanism that updates the current knowledge about the efficiency of the system from the information content of the observed realizations on the performance variable of the process, gives the following result [26]:

$$A(t) = A(1 - X(t) - \sigma_{\omega}^2)^N \quad (3)$$

where $X(t) = (1 / \sigma_{\theta}^2 + \mu t)^{-1}$ and μ is the parameter that converts the number of trials to the equivalent number of time periods.

When time t tends to infinity, a large number of trials, then $X(t)$ tends to zero and the limit on the maximum efficiency will be reached:

$$A^* = A(1 - \sigma_{\omega}^2)^N \quad (4)$$

Dividing (3) by (4) the relative efficiency of the process in period t is equal to:

$$A(t)/A^* = [1 - \frac{(1 / \sigma_{\theta}^2 + \mu t)^{-1}}{1 - \sigma_{\omega}^2}]^N \quad (5)$$

The Jovanovic and Nyarko [26] theory of learning implies that the level of relative efficiency will increase over time with the number of trials, which give noisy information signals about the unknown parameter of the system. The observed value of the relative efficiency at a given moment of time will decrease with the noise of the signals (σ_o^2), with the uncertainty around the mean best practice of the processes (σ_θ^2), and with the complexity of the activity-process (N). However, it increases with the parameter that converts trials into time period effects (μ). Figure 1 represents the shape of the function in (5) for possible scenarios obtained combining high and low values of the parameters that capture the environmental noise of the process, and the uncertainty about the parameter that determines the efficiency of the process. In all cases, it is assumed that there is one trial per unit of time ($\mu=1$).

Figure 1: Learning rate with environmental noise $\sigma_o^2 = 0.2$, system complexity $N = 10$ and changing values of process uncertainty (σ_θ^2).

In theory, the shape of the process performance variable from this learning model can give different shapes, for example an increasing and concave function (when environmental noise is low), or a first increasing convex and later decreasing concave function (when environmental noise is low and complexity N is high). Besides the empirical analysis in the original paper there have been a few additional test of the model published in academic papers.

Table 1: Solutions to the differential equations resulting from combinations in the values of the parameters in equation (1)

Learning Models	Parameters	Flow of Learning $\frac{dA(t)}{dt}$	Cumulative Learning $A(t)$	Graphical Representation of $A(t)$
Constant Learning	$\beta > 0$ $\alpha = 0$ A^* finite	$\frac{dA(t)}{dt} = \beta(A^* - A(t))$	$A(t) = A^* - (A^* - A(0))e^{-\beta t}$	
Learning to Learn	$\beta = 0$ $\alpha > 0$ A^* finite	$\frac{dA(t)}{dt} = \alpha \frac{A(t)}{A^*} (A^* - A(t))$	$A(t) = \frac{A^*}{1 + be^{-\alpha t}}$ where $b = (A^* - A(0)) / A(0)$	
Unlimited Learning	$\beta = 0$ $\alpha > 0$ A^* infinite	$\frac{dA(t)}{dt} = \alpha A(t)$	$A(t) = A(0)e^{\alpha t}$	
Mixed Learning	$\beta > 0$ $\alpha > 0$ A^* finite	$\frac{dA(t)}{dt} = (\beta + \alpha \frac{A(t)}{A^*})(A^* - A(t))$	$A(t) = A^* \frac{1 - \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \Theta e^{-(\beta + \alpha)t}}{1 + \Theta e^{-(\beta + \alpha)t}}$ where $\Theta = \frac{A^* - A(0)}{\frac{\beta}{\alpha} A^* + A(0)}$	

3.-Empirical application: Operational learning in an automobile assembly plant in the early months of operation

In this section, we estimate the time evolution of the TFP of an assembly plant of automobiles in the first five years of operation, and we explain this evolution as the result of the learning processes modelled in the preceding section. The plant belongs to a multinational car manufacturer and began assembling cars regularly in 1983. Our interest is in responding to the question of what is the model of learning, deterministic or stochastic, exogenous learning, learning to learn, or mixed learning, that best explains the empirical evidence for this particular plant. We respond the question comparing the estimated values of the plant's TFP over time with the predicted outcomes from each of the proposed learning models.

3.1 Functional form of the production function and data

The TFP parameter of the production technology in period t , $A(t)$, is calculated as the ratio between the observed number of automobiles assembled in period t , $Q(t)$, and the number predicted from the function $F(K, L; t)$. This function expresses the number of automobiles expected to be assembled in period t given the parameters of the production technology incorporated in the assembly plant when it was built, and given the quantity of capital, K , and labour, L , used in production in period t . Therefore $A(t) = Q(t)/F(K, L; t)$. The actual functional form of $F(\cdot)$ proposed in the paper is of the Cobb-Douglas type, $F(K, L; t) = K(t)^\gamma L(t)^{1-\gamma}$. The parameter γ , elasticity of output to capital, will be empirically estimated with data on inputs and output of the plant at the same time that we estimate the parameters of the respective learning model in the functional form for $A(t)$.

We perform a preliminary statistical analysis of the variables monthly number of assembled cars, capital and labour inputs before deciding the econometric estimation procedure used to obtain the values of the parameters of model. The results give that these variables are unit root non-stationary and co-integrated so the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM), Engle and Granger [17], is the adequate one for the estimation. The

ECM implies estimating a long term and a short term model of the economic process, in our case the production function of the car –assembly plant. The basic model is completed with other explanatory control variables that capture observed alterations in the production process over time, including strikes, holidays, vacations and additional shifts. The complete formulation of the model for one-step ECM estimation (the long term and the short term relationships are estimated at the same time) is as follows:

$$\Delta q_t = \psi_0 + \psi_1 \{q_{t-1} - a(t-1) - \gamma k_{t-1} - (1-\gamma) l_{t-1}\} + \sum_{i=1}^{12} \delta_{i+1} \Delta q_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{12} \delta_{i+14} \Delta k_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{12} \delta_{i+27} \Delta l_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \xi_i DH_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^7 \xi_{i+3} DV_{it} + \xi_{11} DT_t + U_t \quad (6)$$

The low case letters, q , k and l are, respectively, number of automobiles assembled Q , stock of capital, K , and number of employees, L , all expressed in logs and t is the time period in months. Δ is a difference operator so Δq_t means the difference between q_t and q_{t-1} and so on. Since q_t is the number of cars (output) assembled in month t then Δq_t is the rate of output growth in month t . The parameter γ is the elasticity of output to capital input, to be estimated. The term $a(t)$ is the log of TFP value in month t , $a(t) = \ln A(t)$. The variables DH , DV and DT are dummy variables that control for alterations of the normal activity of the assembly plant: strikes (DH), different working days of the month (DV), and changes in the number of production shifts (DT). Finally, U_t is the error term which is assumed to be white noise.

We now explain each of the main terms in equation (6). The term $a(t-1) + \gamma k_{t-1} + (1-\gamma) l_{t-1}$ is the long term relationship between the inputs and output of production, with the variables in logs. The difference $\{q_{t-1} - a(t-1) - \gamma k_{t-1} - (1-\gamma) l_{t-1}\}$ is the deviation between the current level of production in logs, q_{t-1} , and the value predicted by the long term model. The parameter ψ_1 is the speed at which observed and predicted output converge and must have a negative sign for co-integrated variables. The terms $\sum_{i=1}^{12} \delta_{i+1} \Delta q_{t-i} +$

$\sum_{i=0}^{12} \delta_{i+14} \Delta k_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{12} \delta_{i+27} \Delta l_{t-i}$ captures the short term relationship among inputs and

output values obtained from non-anticipated changes in the respective variables, changes in production plans, changes in labour and capital input quantities and so on. The estimation allows for a lag structure of 12 months and δ_{i+T} are parameters to be

estimated. Finally $\sum_{i=1}^3 \xi_i DH_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^7 \xi_{i+3} DV_{it} + \xi_{11} DT_t$ are perturbations of the production process that can be anticipated by the plant managers and include: strikes (DH), different working days of the month (DV), and changes in the number of production shifts (DT). The coefficients ξ_{i+M} are parameters to be estimated.

We use monthly data on output and inputs for the period from September 1984 to March 1992 (91 observations). During this time period the plant was assembling the same basic automobile model so the time series finishes when the plant lay-out, machinery and organization of work were adapted to the new car model to be assembled. Our analysis intends to measure the learning of the plant in the time period when it produced the first car model of its operating life. The output data are number of cars homogenized, so that the output of each and all time periods in the sample is in physical units and homogeneous over time. The inputs are equivalent full-time employees working during the month, and the stock of capital is equal to net plant and equipment at constant 1983 prices at the beginning of month t .

Table 2 shows some descriptive statistics of the data. The cumulative annual growth rate in number of equivalent full time employees and stock of capital at constant prices is very similar, around 1.5%, and smaller than the cumulative annual growth rate in output (number of cars assembled), 5.9%. The difference between output and inputs growth rate, 4.4%, gives a first estimate of the magnitude of productivity growth resulting from learning. Notice that annual growth rates show relatively high volatility (standard deviations of growth rates between 4.3% and 7.8%). Our interest in the detailed empirical analysis is to model the pattern of growth rates over time from the different learning theories.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of inputs and outputs from the assembly plant.

	<i>Labour</i>	<i>Capital</i>	<i>Output</i>
Initial Value	8,383	86,249	21,655
Final Value	9,255	95,225	31,761
Cummulative annual growth rate (%)	1.52%	1.51%	5.85%
Standard deviation annual growth rate (%)	4.30%	7.80%	7.75%

Source Data collected from company files.

3.2.- Estimation of the parameters of the learning models.

3.2.1- Deterministic learning

We estimate the parameters of equation (6) for the case when $A(t)$ is the result of the more general mixed learning model. From Table 1, the mixed learning implies a functional form for $A(t)$:

$$A(t) = A^* \frac{1 - \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \Theta e^{-(\beta+\alpha)t}}{1 + \Theta e^{-(\beta+\alpha)t}} \quad (7)$$

$$\Theta = \frac{A^* - A(0)}{\frac{\beta}{\alpha} A^* + A(0)} \quad (8)$$

Since the function $\ln A(t)$ in (6) is highly non-linear, the estimation of the parameters will follow an iterative process. The first iteration considers the particular case of constant growth rate in the total factor productivity, $\ln A(t) = a(t) = \theta t$, where θ is the parameter of the unlimited learning model. Since the models of constant productivity growth are very frequent in the literature, we present the estimations of the first iteration as the results of particular learning model. The results of estimating model (6) with $a(t-1) = \theta \cdot (t-1)$ appear in the first column of Table 3. The estimated values of the main parameters of the technology, the elasticity of output to capital and the estimate of average productivity growth, are, respectively, $\gamma = 0.393$ ($1 - \gamma = 0.603$) and $\theta = 0.00454$, both statistically different from zero. The estimated value of parameter ψ_l is negative and statistically significant, as expected for co-integrated variables; the estimated value of the speed of adjustment is 0.17536 , which implies that on average each month the system adjusts for 17.5% of the difference to its long-term production value; then it would take less than 6 months to close the gap.

Table 3.- Results from the estimation of equation (6) under different assumptions on the dynamics of TFP that respond to each particular learning model+

	Unlimited Learning (I)	Mixed Learning(II) ¹	Jovanovic-Nyarko(III) ^{1,2}
-Speed of adjustment(ψ_t)	-0.17536** (0.07086)	-0.18432** (0.07134)	-0.14510*** (0.06477)
$\gamma(k_{t-1})$	0.39316*** (0,02472)	0.38665*** (0.01067)	0.38772*** (0.01375)
θ	0.00454*** (0.00108)		
α		0.00685*** (0.00128)	
β		0.03021*** (0.00620)	
σ_ω^2			0.17270*** (0.06471)
σ_θ^2			0.04117*** (0.00543)
R_A^2	0.84082	0.8639	0.84001
Observations	81	81	81

1 Estimated Values $A^*=1.53025$ $A_0=1.04558$

2 Default Parameters $N=10$ $\mu=1$

+Values of the estimated coefficients of the lagged and dummy variables are not reported (See appendix).

Figure 2.I shows the graphical representation of the predicted and observed values of TFP for each month in the estimation period. The estimated value of TFP in month t

is $A_t = \frac{Q_t}{K_t^\gamma L_t^{1-\gamma} e^{bD}}$, where Q_t is the actual number of cars assembled in month t , and the

denominator is the number cars that would be produced as predicted from the model, excluding the constant time trend, θt . Notice that the linear time trend in productivity implicit in the constant growth rate does not match well with the S -shape of the actual values of A_t obtained from the empirical data. This justifies moving to step two on the estimation of the mixed learning model.

In step two, the residual values of A_t obtained from the assumption of constant productivity growth are the dependent variable of equation (7) that, together with (8), summarize the TFP time-trend according to the mixed learning model. We use non-linear regression estimation procedures to fit function (7) to the data and obtain estimates of the parameters β and α . In the estimation, we take as values of A_0 and A^*

the lowest and the highest values of A_t , respectively. Having estimated the parameters, we use (7) and (8) to predict the values of A_t . These values, in logs, are substituted in the place of $a(t-1)$ in equation (6) and the equation is estimated again for new values of γ and of the rest of the parameters. The process is repeated again: use the new estimated parameters of the production function to obtain new values of A_t in $A_t = \frac{Q_t}{K_t^\gamma L_t^{1-\gamma} e^{bD}}$; re-estimate the values of β and α fitting (7) with (8) to these values of A_t . Predict new values of A_t and substitute them in (6) for a new estimation of γ and the rest of the parameters... The estimation process stops when we reach convergence in the values of the parameters.

The values of the estimated parameters from this iterative process, and other information about their statistical significance, are shown in the second column of Table 3, estimation II. The estimated value of the speed of adjustment parameter is 0.18432 and the estimated elasticity of output with respect to capital (labour) is $\gamma = 0.387$ ($1 - \gamma = 0.613$). The estimated values of these parameters are very similar to those obtained in estimation I. The estimated parameters of the learning function are $\beta = 0.00686$ and $\alpha = 0.0302$. All the parameters' estimates are statistically different from zero.

Since the two parameters, β and α , are different from zero, the hypothesis that learning in the assembly plant was driven by a deterministic mixed learning process is not rejected by the data. The speed of learning is then given by the function $0.00686 + 0.0302 \frac{A_t}{A^*}$ where the value of A_t is in the range of $A_0 = 1.046$ and $A^* = 1.530$. Thus, the speed of learning goes from a low value of 0.0275 in the first time period to a high value of 0.0371 in the last month, when the system reaches the maximum productive efficiency. The second term of the speed of learning, the component of learning to learn, contributes substantially more (three times more) than the constant learning parameter to the speed of learning.

Figure 2.II shows the graphical representation of the estimated values of A_t in the last iteration, and the predicted values of $A(t)$ from equations (7) and (8) for the parameter estimates of β and α in estimation II of Table 3. The figure describes the S shape of the data points and of the fitted function. The inflexion point of this function occurs at the

moment in time when the derivative of the function (7) is maximized. Performing the calculation we obtain that the derivative is maximized in December 1987, after 40 months of operation, and the value of the derivative at $t=40$ gives a maximum growth rate of 0.45% .

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Figure 2 Estimated and predicted values of A_t for the three learning models in Table 3.

3.2.2.- Jovanovic and Nyarko's model

The progress in TFP is now represented by equation (5). This function gives the evolution of operating efficiency of the plant over time with four parameters, the noise of the signal, σ_ω^2 , the uncertainty around the mean best practice of the processes, σ_θ^2 , the complexity of the activity-process N , and the parameter that converts trials into time period effects, μ . The functional form of the TFP is highly non-linear and the estimation strategy requires that certain parameters take values fixed in advance. We then fix the value of the parameter $\mu=1$. This means that there is one trial per month, that is the plant managers and workers observe the outcome of the production process and learn from it once a month, a realistic hypothesis. Additionally, the estimation procedure will include two iterative processes. One is the same as was used earlier to estimate the parameters of the TFP function in the case of deterministic mixed learning. The second iterative process involves the estimation of the parameters σ_ω^2 and σ_θ^2 for exogenously given values of the complexity parameter N .

The estimation then proceeds as follows: we first fix a value of N and estimate the parameters σ_ω^2 and σ_θ^2 , together with the rest of the parameters of the production function, substituting $a(t-1)$ in (6) for the equation (5) in logs. The estimation at this stage is performed in a similar manner as in the case of mixed learning. Next, we change the value of N and repeat the estimation of the parameters of the production and learning functions. The process ends when convergence is reached in the R^2 of the regression and in the parameter values.

The results of the estimation are shown in column III of Table 3. The convergence and best fit is obtained for $N=10$. For this value, the estimated elasticity of output with respect to capital is $\gamma=0.388$, statistically different from zero, very close to the value estimated in the other two learning models; the estimated speed of adjustment is now slightly less than in the two deterministic models. All the estimated coefficients for the dummy variables that capture the exogenous shocks are also very similar to those obtained in the other estimations. The estimated values of the other two parameters of the learning model are $\sigma_\omega^2=0.173$ and $\sigma_\theta^2=0.041$, both statistically different from zero. According to these estimates, the uncertainty around the optimal value of the parameter

that drives the efficiency of the process σ_θ^2 is relatively lower than the noise of the signals σ_ω^2 .

The R^2 of the fitted econometric model continues to be above 80%, but a closer look at the plot of the estimated values of the TFP parameter over time, and the plot of the predicted values from the learning model, reveals that the latter does not capture the *S* shape of the former, Figure 2. III. The best estimate of the Jovanovic and Nyarko learning model from the data implies a time evolution of the value of TFP increasing but at a decreasing rate. However, the actual time pattern of the TFP parameter A_t shows a time trend with first increasing and later decreasing growth rates (*S*-shaped pattern).

The comparison of the results from the estimations of the three learning models shown in Table 3 confirms the similarities in the estimated values of the parameters of the production technology, value of elasticity γ around 0.387, and in the estimation of the coefficients of the time dummy variables, among the three (see Appendix 1). The overall fit of the model, R^2 , also similar. The main differences appear in the estimation of the time pattern in the evolution of operating efficiency measured by the value of the TFP parameter at each moment of time. The model that captures the *S* shape of the actual data is the mixed learning model, combining exogenous learning and capabilities for learning to learn. Under mixed learning, the speed of learning increases over time until it reaches its maximum value when the operating efficiency reaches its maximum value too and nothing is left to be learned. Even though the speed of learning at this point of the learning process is the maximum one, the total contribution of learning to TFP growth tends to zero because when the target of efficiency A^* is reached what is left to be learned is zero.

4.- Discussion and conclusion

Productivity growth (increasing output produced, at a higher rate than the rate of increase in the quantity of inputs used in production) is viewed as the main driver of economic prosperity, so there is much ongoing research seeking a better understanding of the sources of productivity growth over time. Solow's [41] ground-breaking paper, pointing to evidence that the aggregate output of an economy tends to grow at a higher

rate than growth in aggregated inputs, identified the difference between the two growth rates as a “residual”. Opening the black box of the residual and better understanding the factors that can make this source of growth larger and more sustainable over time, has attracted the attention of research in all the social and technical sciences.

This paper studies productivity and productivity growth in the much more limited context than the whole economy, namely that of a car-assembly plant in its first years of operation. We have direct knowledge that during the time period of the analysis, September 1984 to March 1992, the production technology remained invariant and the plant assembled the same basic car-model. In this highly controlled and stable production environment, it is most likely that any progress in operating efficiency and productivity will be the result of learning by employees and plant managers in the best ways of doing things within the constraint imposed by the fixed macro technology. Therefore, by studying the time pattern of operating efficiency in terms of TFP observed in the plant each month, we are able to discover which of the learning models proposed in the literature is best represented by the empirical evidence.

Our results indicate that a deterministic learning model, where the speed of learning combines an exogenous constant term and a time-increasing term as a function of relative cumulative past learning, is the model best represented by the empirical data. This mixed learning implies that TFP will increase over time, first at an increasing rate and, after a certain point in time, at a decreasing rate, so the cumulative value of the TFP parameter is *S*-shaped over time. The estimated stochastic learning model of Jovanovic and Nyarko fitted to the same data did not capture the *S* shaped time profile of TFP observed in the data. One tentative explanation of why a deterministic learning is closer to the empirical evidence than the stochastic one is that the assembly plant in this study belongs to a large and experienced world-wide car manufacturer and the engineers and managers who designed the plant probably knew quite well the high standards of performance that would result from operational learning. Notice also that the process of deterministic learning does not mean that there will be no noise around the TFP trend over time; what it does imply is that such noise will not be part of the learning process itself, as it is in the case of the stochastic learning models. Thus, the results of our study do have certain practical implications.

First, our findings are consistent with the hypothesis that knowledge acquisition is a gradual process, so that even when workers and managers know the standard of maximum efficiency, that standard may take some time to be attained. Moreover, under production conditions of stable technology and product characteristics it can be expected that the potential knowledge that can be acquired by some form of learning by experience will be finite, with counterpart value of efficiency level A^* in our analysis. In the particular case of the car-assembly plant, it took between six and seven years to reach the value of A^* , which was around 50% higher than the level of operating efficiency at the beginning of the period. In fact, in January of 1992, coinciding with the end of the complete learning cycle, the management of the company began to introduce major changes in the assembly plant, including the use of more robots in place of workers, as well as changes in the car model to be assembled. Therefore, managers appear to have been aware of the stagnation of productivity growth from operational learning and, once the limit was reached, they introduced major changes in the technology and in the product itself, among other things by attempting to begin a new cycle of learning and productivity growth.

Second, the 50% increase in cumulative TFP does not occur at uniform growth rates over time. Rather, the growth rates vary substantially, first accelerating and later decelerating. In our assembly plant, the maximum monthly growth rate in TFP is estimated to occur in month 40, just in the middle of the time period of observation, and its value was 0.45%. We reject the perpetual or unlimited learning (constant growth rate in TFP for unlimited time) as a good descriptor of the variable that tracks the results of learning and improving; since most studies of productivity growth with macro data assume constant growth rates in TFP over time, the micro results cast doubts that the macro analysis captures what happens at the micro level. The empirical results also reject the hypothesis of a constant learning rate as the best descriptor of the time evolution of TFP. Since the constant learning rate is a special case of the widely-used learning curve, our results suggest that mixed learning should be considered a plausible alternative to the learning curve.

Third, the econometric methodology used in the estimation of the parameters of the model (ECM) distinguishes between “the speed of learning” and “the speed of adjustment” in the working of the assembly plant. The former is a measure of the speed

at which knowledge is acquired, while the speed of adjustment is a measure of how fast what is learned is transformed into higher productive efficiency. The empirical results indicate that in this plant it took between five and six months to adjust from current to target production results (speed of adjustment of 0.183).

Future research should replicate the empirical test of the learning models derived in this paper with data from other production plants or production processes, including learning in machine-scheduling activities and any possible process-improving environment. In this respect, it will be important to verify to what extent the mixed learning model that implies an *S*-shaped time pace of the performance indicator resulting from learning and improving is limited to start-up operations, or not. Future research with data from multiple plants and different industries should also examine whether there is any plant, firm and/or industry characteristic that determines which of the learning models considered in this paper, including the stochastic one, is more likely to occur. An extension closely related to the research done so far would be to examine the cross-car model learning spills over within the same assembly plant as in Levitt, List and Syverson [30]; the de-learning or forgetting process, i.e. the rate at which accumulated knowledge depreciates [7, 44]; and the joint learning of the plant together with the learning of a close external supplier [27].

Finally, another limitation to overcome is incorporating into the analysis the observation of the actions managers take when they learn in contexts of continuous improvement. We have modelled the presumed cycle of action-performance-action, but the only information used in the modelling is the observed performance. As in many manufacturing plants around the world, during the period of study our assembly plant introduced the methods of continuous improvement of TQM and related techniques that will underlie the observed improvement in operating efficiency. It would be of interest for managers who want to know the effect of their decisions to trace the measurement of improvements in TFP after the introduction of a particular innovation in work organization, human resources management, and so on. Research aimed at explaining differences in productivity (and economic performance in general) across firms from different industries and countries, is growing in recent years [10, 16]. The differences in productivity are evaluated at a given moment of time but it would be of interest to investigate the time dynamics of TFP growth rates to infer the underlying learning

model and how this model is related to particular management techniques implemented by firms. The methodology discussed and applied in this paper could be of great help for these purposes.

Appendix 1.- Error Correction Method estimates of parameters of model (6) unreported in the main text (Table 3). All statistically different from zero ($p < 10\%$)

Variable	I.- Unlimited learning	II.- Mixed learning	III.- Jovanovic and Nyarko
DT _t	-0.063789	-0.0640667	-0.066547
DH _{1t}	-0.263477	-0.259767	-0.274161
DH _{2t}	-0.329069	-0.327435	-0.335293
DH _{3t}	-0.161912	-0.161541	-0.162991
DV _{1t}	0.0724797	0.0717038	0.0742428
DV _{2t}	0.146759	0.145737	0.149136
DV _{3t}	-0.207215	-0.206192	-0.211352
DV _{4t}	0.0799451	0.0796149	0.0809149
DV _{5t}	-0.136466	-0.136303	-0.13683
DV _{6t}	-0.184293	-0.183855	-0.187109
DV _{7t}	0.265892	0.264484	0.270482
Δq_{t-2}	0.158715	0.159859	0.157306
Δq_{t-6}	0.185359	0.182958	0.181904
Δk_{t-3}	1.04404	1.06162	1.08947
Δk_{t-8}	0.520535	0.500589	0.517711
Δl_{t-1}	0.777493	0.755712	0.775237
Δl_{t-5}	0.856972	0.848173	0.849558
Δl_{t-9}	-0.756896	-0.778291	-0.726362

Notice that the estimated parameters are all quite similar in the three models, so the differences in results appear mainly in the technology and learning function parameters.

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